

LEARNING HISTORY AND TODAY THROUGH FINE ARTS

National Institute of art and design named after
Kamoliddin Behzod Professional Education:
a student of the 3rd stage of the painting workshop

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Annotation. This article examines the importance of studying history and today through the fine arts. Visual art is a powerful tool that reflects human cultural heritage, providing an opportunity to understand historical events, social processes and cultural change. Through the works of Fine Art, information can be obtained about the life, Customs, religious beliefs, and political situations of mankind in different periods. This article reflects on the role of Fine Arts in the study of history, its impact on the cultural and social situation of today, as well as its application to the educational system of Fine Arts.

Keywords; progress, art, painting, architecture, graphics, sculpture, mental and physical labor, beauty.

Art appeared in very ancient times, because of the progress of the labor process. In the process of labor, human thinking matured, beauty xissi increased, beauty expanded the concepts of comfort and utility. Class society

and with the advent of mental labor, there were major changes in social progress, which began to diverge from physical labor. This was instrumental in the development of science and art. Professional arts and artists emerged during this period.

Indeed, the cultural values that mankind has created do not remain ordinary riches, but reflect in itself human intelligence, thoughts about life

is also a reflecting mirror. Teaching the history of world art, understanding its laws of progress, getting acquainted with rare monuments, studying the feelings of people of the past, life experiences means knowing the formation of ideological

and aesthetic views. This, unconditionally, contributes to the enrichment of life experiences in people, a more extensive and comprehensive approach to life. Types of Fine Arts include painting, architecture, graphics, sculpture.

Fine art is an elegant type of art that combines painting, sculpture, graphics; reflects reality in visual images in its easily progressible spatial forms. The types of Fine Arts, depending on their characteristics, create real existence from objectively existing qualities — volume, color, space, as well as the material form of the subject and the atmosphere of nurhavo, movement and changes, from the emotional concreteness of the image to illusionism. passable. Visual art not only describes what can be seen, but also expands the possibilities of ideological assimilation of the world, reflecting in its works the temporary development of phenomena, one or another part of it (fabula), free narrative, dynamic actions. Visual art also illuminates the mental image of a person, his interaction with others, the psychological and emotional content of the visual State. Sometimes it also surfaces images that do not exist, which are the product of the artist's imagination. Reflects different periods in the history of mankind. Not only the emotional state of the era, but also its ideological essence, political, philosophical, aesthetic and ethical ideas become the content of Fine Art. The expressiveness of the images of Fine Arts allows the artist to express his attitude to a particular phenomenon of life to a high degree; thanks to this, as an active form of knowledge of life, a special role is played in the social life of society, in the decision-making of the mass consciousness of a particular system. Fine Arts also occupy a significant place in social life on the territory of Uzbekistan, reflecting subtle changes in the period and human thought. Zarautsoy's paintings, Khwarazm, Sughd, Bactrian monumental sculpture and paintings are therefore evidence. Medieval Fine Art is stylistically rangebarang, with a wide range of types and hilmahil, during which rare examples of majestic sculpture emerged. Unique sculptural works were created in the regions of India, Indonesia, the Hindikhitoy. In the Middle Eastern countries, where a specific type of miniature was created, in

Medieval European culture, sculpture and painting discovered a specific direction and, meaning on the ground of religious beliefs and worldviews, iconoclastic art prospered. Excellent examples of the synthesis of arts were created in the architectural monuments where the Romanesque style and gotikaaa were built.

Modernization of the educational process in higher educational institutions, in particular, the educational process of Fine Arts, the system of training specialists who will become artists-educators, the development of professional competence of teachers in improving the quality level, arming them with modern professional knowledge, skills and skills related to the field, the development of skills independent of scientific and technical innovation, creative use and In this, ensuring the interconnection, continuity and continuity of the stages of art education; introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies for organizing the educational process of Fine Arts in higher education, ensuring the quality of educational methodological complexes in this regard, constant increase in the literacy of professors and teachers in the use of computers and the internet in the introduction of pedagogical technologies; further development of; the study of advanced foreign experiences in the areas of Visual Arts and engineering graphics determines the composition of the activities of artist-educators in higher educational institutions. As can be seen from the above points, the modernization of the higher education system, in particular, the visual arts education system (visual arts). modern-updated, modern, tekor growth) requires an innovative approach to the learning process. Therefore, the idea of an innovative (English innovation — innovating) approach to visual arts education differs from the traditional approach in that the content and results of education are oriented to the individual, the content of Education, form, method and means are aimed at combining the latest achievements of Science and technology, advanced experiments, modern methodologies. Any innovation introduced into the educational system provides for the availability of information and methodological support. Therefore, the improvement of the content and methods of educational

processes through the study, analysis and generalization and implementation of advanced pedagogical experiments, the use of the capabilities of modern pedagogical and Information Communication Technologies in the introduction of innovation into the educational process of Fine Arts is considered one of the important directions. This, in turn, as effective forms of organizing visual arts training classes, lecture (problem lecture, lecture, visual lecture, virtualtechnological lecture, visual lecture, binary lecture, introductory lecture, lecture-conference, informational lecture, lecture debate, commentator lecture, on-line lecture) as training, videotrining, webinars, internet conferences, innovative teaching methods, problem methods, interactive methods, practical games, educational projects, portfolios, graphic organizers, it brings to the surface the need to use information communication technologies. The importance of interactive methods in applying innovations to the educational process of Fine Arts in higher educational institutions, in particular to the basics of machine-tool academic painting and composition classes, is also unique. The word Interactive is an English word, "inter" means mutual and "act" means to act, and their general content is interactive — that is, to act among themselves. Such types of reciprocal action can include the targeted actions of the “student — teacher” and the “student-student”.

In interactive teaching, the teacher is an active organizer of educational activity, and the student is manifested as a subject of this activity. Interactive teaching is a special organizational form of the development of cognitive activity, characterized by the fact that in the process of interactive teaching, the educational person becomes a subject of interaction from the object of teaching, actively participates in the educational process. Interactive teaching methods are considered when modeling life situations, using role-playing games, solving problems in collaboration. Interactive training will help students not only to form activity, creativity, independence in the process of mastering information, but also to achieve a full-fledged implementation of educational goals. In this, the following

concepts of Education serve as a fundamental basis:

the intensive activity of the teacher is manifested as the main manifestation of the educational activity of the student, who acts as the subject and organizer of this action.

the main basis and result of educational activities, the subject of this activity is the student;

the main indicator of the successful educational activity of the student, the result of which is the formation of skills for learning the thinking methods of the student and the creative solution of practical issues, the ability to act freely, independently;

the main indicator of educational activity is educational assignments. An important place in this is occupied by teaching tactics that develop methods of thinking, cognitive action in the student, the main subject of the educational process;

the process of carrying out educational activities consists in laying the groundwork for the student to master his personal cognitive skills and skills.

In conclusion, today's student will become a worker, a servant, a designer, an engineer, a doctor, a teacher, a lawyer or a military specialist or the creator of some other field in the future. Draw them for each of them, it will be necessary to use it. Graphic knowledge and skills will also be needed to use any simple, tooling tools and customize them. Therefore, it is advisable for everyone to know how to draw, graphic images. One of the main secrets of success for a person in life is to be prepared to take advantage of it when a favorable situation comes. So always the teacher, considering the interest, ability of the student, should be able to increase their creative activity and lead to an independent profession, based on the didactic, unconventional, new method and Idea in the lessons.

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